

Dyslipidemia in the Brazilian population and cardiovascular risk factors: Mini Review

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ABSTRACT Dyslipidemia is one of the most critical risk factors for cardiovascular disease. In Brazil, obesity, inadequate diet and physical inactivity are directly related. This paper aimed to describe the picture of dyslipidemia in the Brazilian population and cardiovascular risk factors, presenting a joint review. The present work consists of a review of the exploratory qualitative approach. In Brazil, the prevention of dyslipidemia can significantly alter cardiovascular morbidity and mortality. Given the importance, it is necessary to develop supplementary tools that can contribute to an improvement in quality of life.

KEYWORDS Cardiovascular diseases, Atherosclerosis, Lipids

Introduction

Lipids are water-insoluble organic substances, but soluble in solvent substances. Lipids have several functions such as participation in nerve impulse transmission and energy storage and are classified into four types: cholesterol, triglycerides, phospholipids and fatty acids[1-2]. Dyslipidemia is a metabolic disorder characterized by changes in serum lipid levels. Changes may include elevation of low-density cholesterol (LDL-c), reduction of high-density cholesterol (HDL-c), and increased triglycerides (TG)[3]. As a result, dyslipidemia is one of the most critical risk factors for cardiovascular disease (CVD)[4].

In Brazil, CVD has been the leading cause of mortality. CVD causes more than 1/3 of deaths in Brazil[5]. This fact can probably be attributed to a lack of investigations in noncommunicable chronic diseases and a high prevalence of risk factors that directly interfere with serum lipid levels, such as obesity, high carbohydrate and fat diets, sedentary lifestyle[6].

Epidemiological assessment of lipid alignment is a crucial methodology considering compliance with health policies aimed

at preventing and reducing cardiovascular risk factors in the population[7,8]. However, studies on the prevalence of dyslipidemia from population surveys in Brazil are still scarce[9].

In this context, the objective of this article was to describe the picture of dyslipidemia in the Brazilian population and cardiovascular risk factors, presenting a joint review.

Methodology

The present work consists of a review of the exploratory qualitative approach.

Obesity

Obesity is worrying due to its association with different comorbidities[10]. In Brazil, overweight and obesity have increased since 1975, following a nutritional transition[11]. Obesity is closely related to the etiology of dyslipidemia, as they share the same source of risk factors[12].

In Brazil, between 2006 and 2012, estimates of the prevalence (%) of overweight in the adult population (≥ 18 years) increased from 11.6% to 17.4%. This increase affects male and female population[13].

This finding may differ according to the region of Brazil[14]. By 2020, it is estimated that 2/3 of the Brazilian adult population is overweight[15]. Among Brazilian children, obesity has been growing rapidly, especially in the age group of 6 to 12 years[16]. The prevalence is around 28% and 40% among children and adolescents[17,18].

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Figure 1: Timeline for the regulatory action in Brazil regarding the ‘trans’ fats[23].

Factors that may explain this finding include carbohydrate and fat diets, physical inactivity. All these factors are primary in the worldwide obesity epidemic and contribute to the onset of cardiovascular disease[19-22]. The cycle of circulatory diseases accounted for 29.4% of all deaths recorded In Brazil in 2007[23].

Carbohydrates, Fats and Sedentary Lifestyle

Dietary changes in Brazil are due to the growing supply of high-calorie processed foods containing high carbohydrate and fat concentrations[24-25]. Excessive carbohydrate and fat intake may contribute to changes in serum lipid levels and increased risk of developing cardiovascular disease[26-28]. According to the National Health Surveillance Agency of Brazil - ANVISA, ice cream, chips, pastries, cakes, cookies are examples of foods rich in trans fat and high consumption in Brazil[29]. Besides, physical inactivity affects 26.3% of the Brazilian population (29.5% of men and 23.5% of women)[30-32].

Given the present situation, a reformulation of processed foods in Brazil was included in the Ministry of Health’s Multiannual Action Plan for 2012–2015 as well as a National Plan for Coping with Noncommunicable Chronic Diseases (NCDs) covering the period between (2011-2022) with the objective of developing and implementing public policies for prevention and control. Figure 1 shows a schedule for regulatory action in Brazil regarding ‘trans’ fats[23].

Conclusion

In Brazil, the prevention of dyslipidemia can significantly alter cardiovascular morbidity and mortality. Given the importance, it is necessary to develop supplementary tools that can contribute even more to improve the quality of life of the Brazilian population.

Conflict of Interest

There are no conflicts of interest to declare by any of the authors of this study.

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References

1. Fahy, Eoin et al. “Lipid classification, structures and tools.” *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta* vol. 1811,11 (2011): 637-47.

2. Bermúdez-Cardona J, Velásquez-Rodríguez C. Profile of Free Fatty Acids and Fractions of Phospholipids, Cholesterol Esters and Triglycerides in Serum of Obese Youth with and without Metabolic Syndrome. *Nutrients*. 2016;8(2):54.

3. Hager, M.R., Narla, A.D. & Tannock, L.R. Dyslipidemia in patients with chronic kidney disease. *Rev Endocr Metab Disord* (2017) 18: 29.

4. Stein, R., Ferrari, F. & Scolari, F. Genetics, Dyslipidemia, and Cardiovascular Disease: New Insights. *Curr Cardiol Rep* (2019) 21: 68.

5. Ribeiro, A. L. et al. Cardiovascular health in Brazil: trends and perspectives. *Circulation* 133, 422–433 (2016).

6. Stadler TAC, Moretti M, Marcelo P, Moretti MP, Sakae TM, Araujo D. Associação dos níveis de dislipidemia entre obesidade tipo I, II e III. *Arq Cat Med*. 2011;40(3):21-4.

7. de Souza LJ, Souto Filho JT, de Souza TF, Reis AF, Gicovate Neto C, Bastos DA, Côrtes VA, et al. Prevalence of dyslipidemia and risk factors in Campos dos Goytacazes, in the Brazilian State of Rio de Janeiro. *Arq Bras Cardiol*. 2003;81(3):249-64.

8. Li P, Yang F, Xiong F, Huo T, Tong Y, Yang S, et al. Nutritional status and risk factors of overweight and obesity for children aged 9–15years in Chengdu, Southwest China. *BMC Public Health*. 2012; 12:636.

9. PEREIRA, Lídia Pitaluga et al. Self-reported dyslipidemia in central-west Brazil: prevalence and associated factors. *Ciênc. saúde coletiva*, Rio de Janeiro, v. 20, n. 6, p. 1815-1824, June 2015.

10. Ferreira HS, Lúcio GM, Assunção ML, et al. High Blood Pressure among Students in Public and Private Schools in Maceió, Brazil. *PLoS One*. 2015;10(11):e0142982.

11. Batista Filho M, Rissin A. A transição nutricional no Brasil: tendências regionais e temporais. *Cad Saúde Pública* 2003; 19(Supl. 1): S181-91.

12. Jung UJ, Choi MS. Obesity and its metabolic complications: the role of adipokines and the relationship between obesity, inflammation, insulin resistance, dyslipidemia and nonalcoholic fatty liver disease. *Int J Mol Sci*. 2014 Apr 11;15(4):6184-223.

13. Malta DC, Andrade SC, Claro RM, Bernal RTI, Monteiro CA. Evolução anual da prevalência de excesso de peso e obesidade em adultos nas capitais dos 26 estados brasileiros e no Distrito Federal entre 2006 e 2012. *Rev Bras Epidemiol*. 2014;17(Supl 1):267-76.

14. Vedana EH, Peres MA, Neves J, Rocha GC, Longo GZ. Prevalence of obesity and potential causal factors among adults in southern Brazil. *Arq Bras Endocrinol Metabol*. 2008;52(7):1156-62.

15. Instituto Brasileiro de Geografia e Estatística (IBGE). Pesquisa de Orçamentos Familiares 2008-2009. Rio de Janeiro: Ministério do Planejamento, Orçamento e Gestão; 2010.

16. Lopes PC, Prado RL, Colombo P. Fatores de risco associados à obesidade e sobrepeso em crianças em idade escolar. *Rev Bras Enferm.* 2010;63(1):73-8.
17. Gerber ZR, Zielinsky P. Risk factors for atherosclerosis in children: an epidemiologic study. *Arq Bras Cardiol.* 1997;69(4):231-6.
18. Moura EC, de Castro CM, Mellin AS, de Figueiredo DB. Lipid profile among school children in Campinas, Brazil. *Rev Saude Publica.* 2000 Oct;34(5):499-505.
19. James WP. The epidemiology of obesity: the size of the problem. *J Intern Med* 2008; 263:336-52.
20. Choi BC, Hunter DJ, Tsou W, Sainsbury P. Diseases of comfort: primary cause of death in the 22nd century. *J Epidemiol Community Health* 2005; 59:1030-4.
21. Palou, A., et al., Obesity: molecular bases of a multifactorial problem. *Eur J Nutr*, 2000. 39(4): p. 127-44.
22. Tomiyama AJ. Stress and Obesity. *Annu Rev Psychol.* 2019 Jan 4; 70:703-718. Epub 2018 Jun 21.
23. Jane Mara Block, Adriana Pavesi Arisseto-Bragotto, Maria Manuela Camino Feltes, Current policies in Brazil for ensuring nutritional quality, *Food Quality and Safety*, Volume 1, Issue 4, December 2017, Pages 275–288.
24. Ataíde Lima RP, de Carvalho Pereira D, Pordeus Luna RC, et al. BMI, overweight status and obesity adjusted by various factors in all age groups in the population of a city in Northeastern Brazil. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2015;12(4):4422– 4438.
25. Bortoli C, Bonatto S, Bruscatto NM, Siviero J. Ingestão dietética de gordura saturada e carboidratos em adultos e idosos com dislipidemias oriundos do Projeto Veranópolis. *Rev Bras Cardiol.* 2011;24(1):33-41.
26. Brasil. Ministério da Saúde (MS). Secretaria de Vigilância em Saúde, Secretaria de Gestão Estratégica e Participativa. *Vigitel Brasil 2009: vigilância de fatores de risco e proteção para doenças crônicas por inquérito telefônico.* Brasília: MS; 2010.
27. Siri-Tarino, Patty W et al. "Saturated Fats Versus Polyunsaturated Fats Versus Carbohydrates for Cardiovascular Disease Prevention and Treatment." *Annual review of nutrition* vol. 35 (2015): 517-43.
28. SANTOS, R.D. et al. I Diretriz sobre o consumo de gorduras e saúde cardiovascular. *Arq. Bras. Cardiol.* 2013, vol.100, n.1, suppl.3, pp.1-40.
29. ANVISA. Gordura Trans. Brasília: ANVISA, 2011. http://www.anvisa.gov.br/alimentos/gordura_trans.pdf.
30. Carter S, Hartman Y, Holder S, Thijssen DH, Hopkins ND. Sedentary Behavior and Cardiovascular Disease Risk: Mediating Mechanisms. *Exerc Sport Sci Rev.* 2017 Apr;45(2):80-86.
31. Nahas MV. Atividade física, saúde e qualidade de vida: conceitos e sugestões para um estilo de vida ativo. 4 ed. Londrina: Editora: Mediograf, 2006.
32. DUMITH, Samuel C. Physical activity in Brazil: a systematic review. *Cad. Saúde Pública* [online]. 2009, vol.25, suppl.3, pp. S415-S426.